

Cost of Fund as a Determinant of Customers' Loan Preference between Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria and Primary Mortgage Banks

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Abstract

High cost of fund has constituted a serious issue that discourages borrowers from accessing funds for housing development. The main objective of this study is to examine finance cost as determinant of customer loan preference between Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) and Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs). The study employed survey design method. The population size was 329,826 and the sample size of 400 respondents from the total population was determined using Yomens (2000) formula. The study adopted questionnaire as a primary source for data collection. The data obtained were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Pearson Correlation with the aid of SPSS Version 25 and the results presented using tables and figures. The result showed 0.996 (strong positive) correlation coefficient (r) between NHF loan 6% interest and NHF loan affordability compared to PMBs at significant level (p=value) 0.000, which was smaller than the significant level α -value ($P < 0.05$). This means that NHF Scheme loan interest rate fixed at 6% per annum by FMBN is the only single digit housing loan servicing interest rate and the cheapest rate obtainable in the housing finance market. The study concluded that finance cost was a determinant of customer loan preference. Customers are always ready to accept a lower interest rate of 6% offered by FMBN compared to 18-23% commercial interest rate provided by PMBs. The study recommends that FMBN should embark on aggressive NHF mobilization drive to widen the net of NHF Contributions' base with a view to increasing the number of its mortgage financing and sustainability of the 6% interest rate to their customers.

Keywords: Finance cost, Housing development, Fund, Interest rate, Mortgage bank

1. INTRODUCTION

The failure of developing housing finance in Nigeria is attributable to the reluctance of the banking system to create sufficient mortgage loans because of the series of risks the universal banks must manage in order to succeed. These risks include credit, interest, and liquidity risks (FMBN Operational Manual, Page II 2015). Government intervention in controlling inflation and interest rates, before the liberation of the banking system, made the situation worse. After liberation, the situation remained difficult to manage due to the absence of requisite financial instruments needed to manage the risks associated with mortgages, largely because of the nascent stage of capital market development in Nigeria. In the quest to provide cheap and affordable home ownership amongst Nigerians, the Federal Government promulgate a Military Decree (Now Act) No. 3 of March 1992 establishing a fund known as "National Housing Fund (NHF)". The major aims and objectives of the Fund was to facilitate the mobilization of funds for the provision of affordable residential houses for Nigerians, provide long-term loans to Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) for on-lending to contributors of the Fund and ensure the constant supply of loans to Nigerians for the purpose of building, purchasing and improvement of residential houses. The Act assigned the responsibility of managing and administering the Fund to Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN). The Bank was also to ensure that the proceeds from the Fund are utilized to finance the housing sector of the economy through wholesale mortgage lending to Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs). The Scheme as it is practised in other countries is meant to be a pool to which the workers contributes and from which they are expected to withdraw or benefit in due time in order to actualize their shelter needs at a fixed-single digit interest rate of 6% per annum, which is not available from the Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) and Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) recognises the relevance of the National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme as the cheapest source of housing finance in Nigeria today, offering

workers and self-employed individuals that are contributing 2.5% of their monthly income and have access, within a short period of contributing, to mortgage loan of up to ₦15 million to build or buy their own houses or renovate and extend existing ones. It is against this background that the present study is designed to examine finance cost as determinant of customer loan preference between Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) and Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs).

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 The Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN)

The Nigerian Building Society (NBS) which subsequently metamorphose into the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) was established in 1956 by Commonwealth Development Corporation (CDC) in conjunction with Federal Government and Eastern Region of Nigeria. Following the introduction of the Indigenisation Policy in Nigeria in 1973, the Federal Government acquired 100 percent ownership of the NBS and consequently renamed it the “Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria” (FMBN Act No. 7 of 1977). The FMBN was reorganised in 1978 by the Federal Government of Nigeria to accelerate housing delivery in the country. It is expected to provide mortgage lending on a nationwide basis at rates of interest below the market rates. The FMBN, at this time, source its funds from the deposit’s mobilisation and equity contributions by the Federal Government (50%), the Central Bank of Nigeria (30%) and Nigeria Social Insurance Trust Fund (20%). The FMBN under the decree became the apex regulatory institution in the mortgage sector responsible for licensing, regulating and supervising the Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) as second tier housing finance institutions. With the new decree, the PMBs were to mobilize deposits (i.e., savings) from the public and grant housing loans to individuals; while the FMBN mobilizes capital funds for the Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs). The establishment of PMBs was expected to enhance private sector participation in housing finance in Nigeria (FMBN Operational Manual, Page II 2015). The FMBN started the management and administration of the contributory savings scheme known as the “National Housing Fund (NHF)” (Act 3 1992). The NHF is a pool that mobilizes long-term funds from Nigerian workers, banks, insurance companies and the Federal Government to advance loans at soft interest rates to its contributors. In 1994, the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN), with the promulgation of the (FMBN Act 82, 1993) and the (Mortgage Institutions Act of 1989) was accorded the status of the apex mortgage institution and thus ceded its retail function to an autonomous company, Federal Mortgage Finance Limited (FMFL) which was carved out of the FMBN in December 1993, itself fully owned by the Federal Government of Nigeria. The FMBN witnessed a reform with the appointment of Prof. Akin Mabogunje as Chairman of the Presidential Technical Board (PTB) of the Bank inaugurated by President Obasanjo to implement the Federal Government’s white paper on the Governor Peter Odili’s (former Rivers State Governor) Report on Housing and Urban Development and establish the institutional structures for a virile housing finance system in Nigeria. The restructuring brought about the merger of FMFL with FMBN to form a new FMBN in January 2004 and repositioned to effectively perform its mandate as a secondary mortgage institution; developing the primary mortgage market and bridging the gap between the mortgage and capital markets through a financial intermediation process (FMBN Mortgage News Journal, Volume I, No.3, Page 5, October 2015). Following the reform of the housing sector based on the Federal Government 2002/2006 National Policy on Housing and Urban Development, The FMBN was restructured into a Federal Government Sponsored Enterprise (FGSE) with more focus on secondary mortgage and capital market functions (Federal Government Policy on Housing and Development, 2002-2006). The FMBN was now to play the critical role of developing a robust mortgage finance system for the country. To meet its mandate, the FMBN has shifted operational emphasis to expand its functions from only social housing on-lending under the National Housing Fund (NHF) to include commercial on-lending for housing, commercial mortgages refinancing, mortgage purchasing & warehousing and Mortgage-Backed Securitisation (MBS). The FMBN now finances mortgages created by Primary Mortgage Bank (PMBs) under the National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme and also gives Estate Development Loans (EDL) to Real Estate Developers to build mass housing for NHF Contributors. The overall focus of FMBN is to promote the delivery of affordable and modern houses to Nigerians.

The functions of FMBN can be summarised as follows (Olowe Ayo, 2017):

1. Provide long-term credit facilities to PMBs in Nigeria to enable them grant comparable facilities to

individuals desiring to acquire houses of their own.

2. Encourage and promote the emergence and growth of PMBs to serve the need of housing delivery in all parts of Nigeria.
3. Mobilizing both domestic and offshore funds into the housing sector.
4. Linking the capital market with the housing industry, establishing and operating a viable secondary mortgage market to support the primary mortgage market.
5. Collect, manage and administer contributions to the National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme in accordance with the provision of the NHF Act No. 3 of 1992.

2.2 Role of Primary Mortgage Banks (PMB) in the Housing Delivery

The Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) are deposit taking banks established for the purpose of providing mortgage financing in Nigeria. They operate retail banking services through mobilization of savings for the development of the housing sector in Nigeria. They, thus, perform traditional banking functions except that they are not members of the Nigerian clearing system. They can also not deal in foreign exchange. PMBs are important deposit taking institutions competing with clearing banks and other financial institutions to obtain deposits from customers, (Act No. 53 of 1989). Under the Act, the licencing and supervision of the PMBs are the exclusive responsibilities of Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN). In 1998, amended Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Act 1998, FMBN transferred the supervisory powers of the PMBs to the CBN. A Primary Mortgage Bank duly licensed by the CBN under the Mortgage Institutions Act and accredited by FMBN shall qualify to apply for the loan from the Fund on behalf of NHF contributors based on certain terms and conditions. No Mortgage Bank shall be allowed to apply for the NHF loan without obtaining from CBN, a written approval/clearance of its capacity to be considered for such facilities. Any loan granted by FMBN to PMBs shall be secured by a block of existing mortgages under cover of Sales and Administration Agreement to be executed between FMBN and the PMBs. The Sales and Administration Agreement referred to above, shall be registrable in the Land Registry along with the Deed of Assignment of Mortgages to which the Agreement relates. The NHF loan to PMBs is limited to 50% of its current Shareholders Fund per transaction and the loan is lent to the PMBs at 4% interest rate per annum on annuity basis, payable monthly irrespective of whether or not the Mortgagor is making repayments. The interest rate for each loan shall be fixed for the duration of the loan. Perfected Fund Mortgage is the ultimate security for loans on-lent to individuals through the PMBs. However, the underlisted are acceptable as interim securities (Olowe Ayo, 2017):

- a. Property owned by the PMB or its Directors.
- b. Treasury bills.
- c. Bank guarantee.
- d. Insurance company guarantee.
- e. Block of existing mortgages.
- f. Or any other Financial Instrument that the Board of FMBN may approve.

Loans to finance home construction/renovation are to be released in three instalments to the PMB, who will in turn release same to the individual borrowers. Loans for outright purchase are released in one lump sum. Any PMB that refuses to disburse the loan to the beneficiary applicant within 60 days of receipt of the NHF loan funds will be sanctioned (BOFIA, 1997). The PMB must show evidence of its NHF remittance to FMBN up to the month preceding the date of disbursement. Any PMB that is in default of loan repayment on the previous loans granted for a maximum period of three months shall be denied further access to NHF loan facility.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Nubor (2017), examined the challenges of housing finance and its implications on home ownership by the low- and medium-income earners in Nigeria. The focus on mortgage finance is very prominent in the study because housing provision requires huge capital which is often beyond the capacity of the low- and medium-income groups in Nigeria. Housing finance to this group of people has often been fingered as one of the most formidable constraints in the housing sector in Nigeria. Raising finance for housing development has become more like an insurmountable barrier making credit financing very inevitable. Structured and unstructured questionnaires were designed for the study to gather primary data. The study population

comprises of the low- and medium-income earners within the study area and the sample size was 400. The quantitative method, descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis and presented in tables and charts. The result of the analysis showed that the difficult requirements laid down by the Primary Mortgage banks (PMBs) to grant housing loans have prevented the low- and medium-income earners from having access to the National Housing Fund (NHF) through the PMIs. The informal sources' window as an alternative source of housing finance was suggested for further study.

Adetiloye, Akinjare, Akhanolu and Tochukwu (2016), reviewed the assessment of the contribution of Primary Mortgage Institutions (PMIs) to housing finance in Nigeria. The study finds out that Mortgage financing represents the genuine means of housing in the world's developed economies and is also more of a challenge in developing countries. The mortgage industry in Nigeria involves few active players which are often banks subsidiaries and a collection of smaller inadequate mortgage institutions. These institutions include semi government agencies, mortgage banks and building societies. Mortgage financing was fingered as the most difficult constraints in the Nigerian housing sector. One of the major problems identified was the inadequate supply of long-term funds which represents the major means of providing mortgages. Questionnaires as a primary source of data collection were adopted. The population size was about 250 staffs working in Union Homes Savings and Loans PLC whilst 54 respondents represented the sample size. Data analysis and presentation were done using tables. The study showed clearly the problem of the mortgage industry in Nigeria which include; high interest rate tagged to PMI funded loans, the cumbersome process in the NHF application, PMI's low capital base among others. The study recommended that sound economic and monetary policies can curb and overcome the negative effect of inflation in the economy which in turn may affect housing finance was suggested.

Udoka and Kpataene (2017), examined mortgage financing and housing development in Nigeria. The study focussed on finance as being more prominent because the provision of houses requires huge financial resources which most of the low-income earners in Nigeria are unable to afford. The problem of inadequate provision of housing in Nigeria stems from the inability of the National Housing Fund (NHF) to fund housing development. Other problems identified were high inflation and interest rates, high cost of building materials, insufficient wage and income distribution, low savings culture and also the problem of land tenure system in some parts of the country. The study also finds out that existing realities showed that the potentials of the mortgage industries remain untapped as it is constrained by factors undermining the access and sustainability of mortgage finance by the average poor citizen in Nigeria. The study identified the problem of housing delivery in Nigeria as becoming a source of concern to many, as it affects the well-being of the citizens as well as the growth and development of the economy. The study also finds out that a major threat of housing arises especially in the urban centres in Nigeria where inadequate supply of houses relative to demand is experienced. The study included that the major constraints inhibiting the provision of housing in Nigeria is the inability of the mortgage institutions to carry out their primary objective of providing fund for housing development in Nigeria. Secondary data were used in this study. The ex-post facto research was adopted. The techniques of data analysis adopted for this research include the Unit root test, Co-integration, Error Correction Model (ECM) and the Granger casualty test. The result of the findings showed that mortgage loan has significant and positive impact on the development of housing in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study suggested Mortgage Institution strategies for deposits mobilization and government creation of an enabling environment for private housing sector in housing development in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design and Population

A survey design was used for this research to collect data. The population of the study was 329,826 representing the total Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) registered employees for National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme in five State Offices (Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Ekiti and Kwara) under the Ibadan Zonal Office as at December, 2019.

3.2 Sample Size Determination for the Study

Simple Random Sampling (SRS) technique was adopted for this study because all the elements of the population have equal chance of being selected. The sample size from the total population was determined

using the Yomens (2000) formula:

$$SS = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where,

SS is the sample size; N is the population size and e is the tolerable error in investigating the population.

Therefore,

$$SS = \frac{329,826}{1 + 329,826(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{329,826}{825.56} = 399.52$$

Approximated to 400

3.3 Research Instrument

The study adopted questionnaire as a primary source of data collection instrument because it provides a greater degree of responses when administered properly. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: the first part deals with the personal data of the NHF registered employee and FMBN State Office for NHF Remittance; and the second part contains thirty (30) questions that attempt to seek inputs on the operations of National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme. A total of 400 questionnaires were administered in which 80 questionnaires were given to FMBN NHF Mobilization Officer of each of the five State Offices for distribution to NHF Desk Officer of the registered organisations' employees. However, 380 questionnaires were returned and therefore considered satisfactory for analysis, representing 95% response rate which was good enough for reliability and valid conclusion. Cronbach Alpha coefficient was used to test the reliability of the instrument, using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25. The Cronbach Alpha value for the overall scale when the items are standardized was 0.780 and when the items are not standardized, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient value for this study was 0.793 which shows strong reliability.

Table 1: Reliability Statistic

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach' Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Item
0.793	0.780	30

Source: SPSS Reliability Analysis, 2020

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data obtained from primary source were analysed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 25) and the results were presented using both descriptive and inferential statistics to examine the Finance cost as determinant of customer loan preference between Federal Mortgage Bank (FMBN) and Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Respondents Bio-Data Representation

The data obtained from the returned questionnaire of 380 respondents were analysed and presented below:

Table 2: Analysis of the Questionnaires Administered

Respondents	Oyo	Osun	Ondo	Ekiti	Kwara	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Number of copies returned	72	80	68	80	80	380	95
Number of copies not returned	8	0	12	0	0	20	5
Total number of questionnaires	80	80	80	80	80	400	100

Source: Field Survey Result, 2020

Analysis of table 2 above shows that 400 questionnaires were administered on National Housing Fund

(NHF) Scheme registered employees in the study areas, out of which 380 were returned with substantial information; representing 95% while 20 were not returned, representing 5%.

Table 3: Gender of the Respondents

FMBN State Office	Male		Female		Total
	No of Respondents	%	No of Respondents	%	
Oyo	44	17	28	24	72
Osun	60	23	20	17	80
Ondo	56	21	12	10	68
Ekiti	64	24	16	14	80
Kwara	40	15	40	35	80
Total	264	100	116	100	380

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Analysis of table 3 above indicates that 264 respondents representing 69% were male while 116 respondents representing 31% were female.

Table 4: Age of the Respondents

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-30 years	4	1
31-40 years	144	38
41-60 years	232	61
Total	380	100

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Analysis of table 4 above shows that 4 respondents representing 1% falls between the age range of 18-30 years. Furthermore, 144 respondents representing 38% were between 31-40 years. In the same vein, 232 respondents representing 61% were between 41-60 years.

Table 5: Period of Contribution into the NHF Scheme

Period of Contribution to NHF	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 6 months	12	3
6 months – 5 years	140	37
Above 5 years	200	53
Not Applicable	28	7
Total	380	100

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Analysis of table 5 indicates that 12 respondents representing 3% contributed into the National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme below 6 months and as a result not qualified to apply for the NHF Loan as per the Act. Furthermore, 140 respondents representing 37% contributed into the Scheme between 6 months to 5 years whilst 200 respondents representing 53% have contributed into the Scheme above 5 years. However, 28 respondents representing 7% did not state the period of their contributions into the NHF Scheme.

4.2 Examination of Research Question

Table 6: Responses on NHF Loan Interest rate fixed at 6% per annum

NHF Loan Interest	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Disagree	8	2
Disagree	12	3
Neutral	16	4
Agree	48	13
Strongly Agree	296	78
Total	380	100

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Table 6 above shows that 296 respondents representing 78% strongly agreed that National Housing Fund (NHF) Loan interest rate fixed at 6% per annum according to the NHF Act 1992 being managed by the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) as a single digit interest rate is the cheapest rate that is obtainable in the housing finance industry/market. In the same vein, 48 respondents representing 13% agreed that NHF Scheme established by the Federal Government to provide the cheapest financing option for Nigerian workers both in formal and informal sectors of the economy who are in need of social housing. The interest rate is fixed at 6% per annum to enable the NHF contributor afford and service their mortgage loan.

Table 7: Responses on NHF Loan Interest Being lower, compared to PMBs Housing Loan Interest

NHF Loan – PMBs Loan Interest	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Disagree	8	2
Disagree	12	3
Neutral	20	5
Agree	12	3
Strongly Agree	328	87
Total	380	100

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Table 7 above indicates that 328 respondents representing 87% strongly agreed that National Housing Fund (NHF) loan interest fixed at 6% per annum is disbursed by the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) at 4% interest rate through the Primary Mortgage Bank (PMB) and in turn released to NHF Contributor at the rate of 6% per annum. The mortgage loan facility obtainable from Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) ranges from commercial interest rates of 18-23% that is too high for average civil servant to afford.

Table 8: Responses on NHF Loan Affordability compared to PMBs Mortgage Loan

NHF Loan Affordability – PMBs Mortgage Loan	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Disagree	8	2
Disagree	8	2
Neutral	16	4
Agree	24	6
Strongly Agree	324	86
Total	380	100

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Table 8 above reflects that 324 respondents, representing 86% strongly agreed that National Housing Fund (NHF) loan facility from Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) at the rate of 6% fixed interest rate is cheaper and affordable to the NHF contributors when compared with Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) housing loan facility which is at commercial interest rate of between 18-23% and fluctuate subject to microeconomic policy of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN).

Table 9: Responses on NHF Loan Repayment tenure longer than PMBs

NHF Loan Tenure – PMBs Mortgage	Tenure Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Disagree	16	4
Disagree	32	8
Neutral	8	2
Agree	52	14
Strongly Agree	272	72
Total	380	100

Source: Primary Data processed, 2020

Table 9 shows that 272 respondents representing 72% strongly agreed that NHF loan repayment tenure of maximum of 30 years subject to NHF Contributor's current age as at the time of loan application and his/her years in the service of employment is longer than what can be obtained from Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) which has a limit of 15 years. Fifty-two (52) respondents representing 14% agreed that the NHF loan repayment period has a longer tenure when compared with PMBs repayment plan.

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

The data obtained from primary source were analysed with aids of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 25) and the hypothesis of the study was tested using Pearson Correlation coefficient to determine the correlational relationship between some dependent and explanatory variables on the perceptions of Finance cost as determinants of customer loan preference between Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) and Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs).

Re-Statement of Research Question

Is the National Housing Fund (NHF) Loan interest offered by Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) affordable compared to Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) Loan interest?

Re-Statement of Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was tested in order to achieve the aims of this study:

Ho: National Housing Fund (NHF) Loan interest offered by Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) is not affordable compared to Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) Loan interest.

Table 10: Pearson Correlations Matrix (H_0)

		Correlations	
		NHF Loan 6% Interest	NHF Loan Affordability to PMBs
NHF Loan 6% Interest	Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.996**
	Sig. 2-tailed (p)		.000
	N	5	5
NHF Loan Affordability to PMBs	Pearson Correlation (r)	.996**	1
	Sig. 2-tailed (p)	.000	
	N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Version 25 Processed Data for Null Hypothesis, 2020

Table 10 above shows that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r) between National Housing Fund (NHF) Loan 6% Interest and National Housing Fund (NHF) Loan Affordability to Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) is 0.996 which is strong positive correlation coefficient at the significant level ($p = \text{value}$) 0.000 based on sample size ($n = 5$). The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The value of ($p = 0.000$) is lower than the conventional value of alpha (α) of 5% acceptable level of significance. This means that there is a statistically significant relationship between NHF Loan 6% Interest and NHF Loan Affordability to PMBs. Since the p-value (0.000) is smaller than the significance level α -value ($P < 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that National Housing Fund (NHF) Loan interest offered by Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) is affordable compared to Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) Loan interest.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

Findings from this study revealed that the National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme loan interest rate fixed at 6% per annum by the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) is the only single digit housing loan servicing interest rate and the cheapest rate that is obtainable in the housing finance industry/market. It is far lower and affordable compared with the Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) commercial interest rate of 18-23 percent which was considered too high for any average NHF Scheme contributors to afford. Housing affordability is a function of household income, price of the property and taste of the individual. The NHF loan repayment tenure of maximum of 30 years period subject to NHF contributors' current age as at the time of loan application and his/her years in the service of employment is longer than what can be obtained from PMBs which has a limit of 15 years period.

Findings from existing research revealed that mortgage financing has often been fingered as the most difficult constraints in the Nigerian housing sector. One of the major problems has been the inadequate supply of long-term funds which represents the major means of providing mortgages. The research (Nubor, 2017) has shown clearly the problem of the mortgage industry in Nigeria which include; high interest rate tagged to PMB funded loans, the cumbersome process in the NHF application, PMB's low capital base among others. Also, the problem of inadequate provision of housing in Nigeria stems from the inability of the NHF to fund housing development.

The result of the analysis of the previous research indicated that the difficult requirements laid down by the PMBs to grant housing loans have prevented the low- and medium-income earners from having access to the National Housing Fund through the PMBs. The study also revealed that if the informal sources are advanced upon, it can serve as an alternative source of housing finance. Raising finance for housing development has become more like an insurmountable barrier making credit financing very inevitable. However, the results of the analysis of the current study showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between NHF Loan 6% Interest and NHF Loan Affordability to PMBs. We conclude that Finance cost was a major determinant of customer loan preference between NHF loan of 6% interest offered by Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) and Primary Mortgage banks (PMBs) commercial mortgage loan interest which ranges from 18-23%.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that National Housing Fund (NHF) Scheme established by the Federal Government is to provide the cheapest financing option for Nigerian workers both in the formal and informal sectors of the economy who are in need of social housing. The interest is fixed at 6% per annum to enable the National Housing Fund (NHF) contributors afford and service their mortgage loan obligations. National Housing Fund (NHF) loan repayment tenure of maximum of 30 years subject to National Housing Fund (NHF) contributor's current age as at the time of loan application and his/her years in the service of employment is longer than what can be obtained from Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) which has a limit of 15 years.

From the research work conducted, the following recommendations are made:

- a) The Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) should embark on aggressive NHF mobilization drive to widen the net of NHF Contributions' base with a view to increasing the number of its mortgage financing and sustainability of the 6% interest rate to their customers.
- b) The Federal Government, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and Nigerian Social Insurance Trust Fund (NSITF), the shareholders of FMBN to review upward the capital base of the bank from ₦ 5 billion to ₦500 billion to enable it have more liquidity that will supplement the NHF Collections for expansion of NHF loan financing operations.
- c) The FMBN should develop a new thinking on how to have additional funding source outside the NHF Scheme for its mortgage finance operations.

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